

SMART COMPOSITE SURFACE WITH *IN-SITU* TUNABLE ADHESION BEHAVIOR

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Keywords: *Smart composite surface, Shape memory polymer, In-situ tunable adhesion, Reversible behavior*

1 Introduction

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are smart materials that can recover a pre-determined permanent shape from a temporarily fixed shape upon external stimuli such as heat, pH, light, electric fields, etc. General SMPs show one-way actuation behavior, i.e., upon external stimuli they recover the permanent shape, but subsequent applied stimuli do not induce the shape change of SMP into the temporary one. In a certain situation (under bias load), two-way actuation behavior can be observed [1], i.e., subsequent stimuli bring about another temporary shape. This phenomenon was demonstrated through smart composites of elastomer and shape memory polymer [2]. Various applications have been developed using SMP, among which smart surfaces have attracted much attention from materials scientist and process engineers [4] because surfaces can be modified effectively using the shape change of SMPs. In this study we investigated how the microstructural morphologies of patterned surfaces using SMPs are changed according to stimuli and also whether smart adhesion (e.g., in-situ tunable adhesion) can be realized in such patterned surfaces. The adhesion of dusts or pollutant to solid surfaces is often determined by their wettability. The wettability of a surface can be sophisticatedly controlled, demonstrating self-cleanable surface, which can be broadly applied to develop smart electronic cases, furnishings, garments etc. [3]. Most of studies for this self-cleanable surface have been carried out relying on the chemical modifications (functional groups) of surfaces. In this study, we used SMPs to develop smart composite surface, the adhesion of which can be controlled in *in-situ* manner, i.e., upon stimuli applied, the adhesion of the surface is weakened so as to be easily taken away from the substrate, otherwise its adhesion is strong enough to sustain the environmental

conditions. In followings, we discuss efficient methods for preparing such smart surfaces with tunable actuation behavior, patterning their surfaces, and characterizing in-situ tunable adhesion.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

To prepare SMP film, poly(cyclooctene) (PCO, Evonik Industries Vestenamer 8012) and dicumyl peroxide (DCP) (>98% purity, Aldrich) were used as received without any further purification (see Fig. 1 for the chemical formula). PCO (10wt%) and DCP (0.2wt%) were dissolved in toluene and stirred for 24h at 80 °C. The solution was dried in hood, obtaining uniformly mixed compounds.

2.2 Micro-patterning of SMP film surface

In order to fabricate poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS, sylgard 184A) replica mold, a master mold was prepared to manufacture a pillared surface. The prepolymer of PDMS and the curing agent (sylgard 184B) were mixed at a weight ratio of 10:1 and stirred for uniform mixing. The mixture was then poured to the master mold. To remove bubble, it was defoamed in the vacuum chamber for 30 minutes under mTorr pressure condition. The defoamed PDMS was cured at 100 °C for 30 min. The cured PDMS replica mold was then detached carefully from the master mold without any damages.

Prepared PCO-DCP compound was melted at 80 °C, poured into the PDMS replica mold and pressed to fill the gap between the mold and the compound. It was heated to 180 °C for 30 min to cure the PCO-DCP compound. The cured PCO was then detached

from the replica mold carefully. Finally, the SMP film with pillared surface was fabricated.

2.3 Characterization of actuation behavior

To characterize the shape memory behavior of the patterned surface on the smart composites, first, the SMP films with micro pillars were heated and loaded at a slant angle (see Figure 2 for detailed diagram). The SMP films were then cooled to fix the pressed pillars on the composite surface. Finally, the SMP films were heated again to recover the original shape of the pillar. These procedures were carried out in an environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM).

To characterize the shape memory behavior of individual micro-pillar made of the SMP, pillars were detached from the surface and tested using modified shape memory method as shown in Fig.3. This test was carried out in a micro-indenter equipped with heating device and nanoindenter.

In-situ tunable adhesion behavior of the composite surface was also characterized within a thermo-mechanical tester (built in laboratory). The adhesive force was measured during the thermo-mechanical testing cycle to investigate the tunable behavior of the smart composite surface.

2.4 Thermo mechanical properties

The optical microscope, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and the atomic force microscope (AFM, XE100, Park Systems) were used to characterize the morphology of the smart surface.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, 823E, Mettler Toledo) was used to analyze the thermal properties of of PCO-DCP bulk compounds. The heat flow of the bulk compound was measured from 0 °C to 200 °C during two cycles.

The thermo-mechanical behavior of the SMP was characterized using a tensile tester with an environmental chamber. The tester used in this study includes all four steps in the conventional shape memory test in Fig. 4. The sample was heated to 60 °C and elongated 40 %. Under a fixed strain of 40 %, the sample was cooled to 20 °C. When the load was released, some shrinkage took place but a temporary shape was formed. Lastly, the samples

were heated to 60 °C while maintaining zero-load recovery, resulting in the sample's retraction to the memorized permanent shape. During the thermo-mechanical test, the shape fixity and the recovery rates were evaluated by the following equations

$$\text{Fixity}(\%) = \frac{\varepsilon_u}{\varepsilon_m} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recovery}(\%) = \frac{\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon_p}{\varepsilon_m} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.5. Contact angle measurement

The wettability of the micro-patterned surfaces on the SMP was evaluated by measuring the contact angle (CA). Static CA measurement employing a drop method was carried out using a laboratory-made goniometer. As the patterned surface was thermally programmed from permanent, to temporary shape, the contact angles were measured.

2.6 Characterization of adhesive behavior

The adhesive strength of the composite surface was measured using a single lab shear adhesion test method. To minimize the effect of the surface roughness, the flat slide glass was used as an adhesion substrate. The slide glass was cleaned with following three steps to remove contaminants. First, it was cleaned with acetone with sonication. It was then washed with ethanol with sonication. Finally it was cleaned with IPA with sonication. After that the slide glass was gently blown by the nitrogen gun to remove residual solvent.

After placing the SMP film with micro-pillared surface on a slide glass, it was heated to 80 °C to melt the crystalline segment of the SMP and pressed with a pressure of 20, 40, 60 N/cm² to make contact surface between the SMP and the cleaned slide glass. Under the constant stress condition, it was cooled to room temperature. The sample was transferred to an oven chamber with temperature of 30 °C and was stored for 1 h before the adhesion test. The prepared sample was loaded at a constant displacement rate of 2 mm/min until complete fracture occurs, during which the load and displacement were recorded. The pull-off strength

was calculated from $\sigma = F_p / A$, where F_p and A represent the peak load and cross-sectional area ($10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$), respectively.

In order to ensure the reliability, all of experiments were performed seven times, among which five data were selected to calculate the mean and standard deviation of pull-off strength. The schematic diagram of this experiment was presented at Fig. 3

3 Results and Discussion

To determine the transition temperature of SMP, its thermal behavior was analyzed through DSC. Fig. 5 shows that the melting peak of pure PCO was observed at $56 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the curing temperature was determined to $176 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in first heating process. It can be confirmed that the crystallization temperature of the switch segment of SMP was $21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in first cooling process and the melting temperature of cured PCO was observed at $42 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the second heating. Comparing the melting temperature and enthalpy of fusion between pure PCO and cured PCO, the melting peak was shifted to lefthand side and the enthalpy of fusion decreased after curing process. In case of pure PCO (without curing process), the chain mobility is high. For the samples with high crosslink density, the polymer chains are restricted against diffusion and conformational rearrangement. As a result, the total degree of crystallinity and the size of crystal was reduced as the contents of the DCP increased. The former is related to the decreasing of enthalpy of fusion. The latter inferred from the left-shifting of the melting temperature (see Fig.6). Using the above results, low temperature for the crystallization was set at $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the high temperature for melting was set at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. To characterize the shape memory property of the cured PCO, the conventional one-way shape memory test was conducted (see Fig. 7 for detailed results). The first strain was set to 40%. The fixity and the recovery ratio were calculated as 91.8% and 93.5%, respectively, confirming that the cured PCO has excellent shape memory performance.

. Cured PCO exhibits strong adhesion to the substrate when it was heated and pressed. PDMS with low surface energy was used as a replica mold. As a result, the SMP films with wall and pillar

pattern on surface were manufactured without being damaged when the sample was detached from replica mold. The optical image of the surface is shown in Fig.8.(a). The top and bottom were formed periodically, and the distance between top is approximately $1.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. To investigate precise surface morphology, AFM was used (see Figure 9). The defects, which were not observed in the optical microscope, were shown in Fig. 9 (b). Fig.9.(c) shows that the distance between top is all the same ($1.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). The height of the wall was about 100 nm .

Figure 10 shows SEM images of the SMP films with micro-pillared surface ($2 \mu\text{m}$ interval). To confirm the shape memory properties of the micro-pillars on SMP film surface, a modified shape memory test in Figure 2 was conducted. Figure 11 shows the optical images of each step of the test procedures. As shown in Figure 11 (a), the micro-pillars were uniformly fabricated on the smart surface. The micro-pillars were deformed and fixed (see Figure 11 (b)). Finally it was recovered to the original shape upon heating (Figure 11 (c)). We observed that a portion of pillars couldn't be recovered for large force case. We are investigating deformation limits (and thus force limit) that can ensure the complete recovery of the micro-pillars under various forces and tilted angles.

To characterize the force limit of individual SMP pillar, the shape memory test was conducted for the pillar. The pillar was compressed with a nano-indenter in SEM (see Fig. 10). The stress-strain curve was presented in Fig. 11.

The morphological effect on surface wettability was investigated by measuring the contact angle. Fig.14 shows that the contact angles increased as the micro-pillars were more densely introduced. Note that the surface area of the SMP film was increased by the micro-pillars [5]. Fig. 15 shows that the contact angle of the patterned surface on the SMP was dramatically changed according to temperature stimuli, i.e., in the permanent shape the contact angle of the patterned surface was around 130° while it was decreased to about 100° for the temporary shape. Note that the temporary shape was programmed by pressing the micro-pillars at a temperature higher than the transition temperature of

the SMP, followed by cooling to room temperature. Upon heating the micro-pillars were recovered to the permanent shape, thus returning the contact angle to the original one. Systematic experiments will be performed to investigate the effect of micro-pillar geometry.

The cured PCO does not show good adhesion to glass at room temperature. When it was heated to melting temperature, however the adhesion changed to have strong stick to a glass. The adhesive property of a sample, which was heated and pressed to glass, was remained after cooling under the crystallization temperature. Using this property, the adhesion state was formed and shear stress was applied to measure the shear pull-off strength.

The graph of preload vs shear pull-off strength was shown in Fig. 16. When the preload was 20 N/cm², the shear pull-off strength was measured to 50 N/cm². This low value was due to small contact area, and thus weak. When the preload was increased from 20 N/cm² to 40 N/cm², the pull-off strength increased significantly. Over 40 N/cm², the increase rate became gentle and converged to approximately 80 N/cm². As described above, when the preload was 40 N/cm², most of the surface was contacted to the glass. The factors determining the pull-off strength of adhesion was contact area, not the preload. Therefore, the 60 N/cm² was used as the base preload in the following experiments.

The graph of displacement vs shear pull-off strength was shown in Fig.17. In case of solid line graph, the sample was prepared the method above, and the pull-off strength was measured at room temperature. It was shown that the peak was formed at a displacement of about 0.3mm under 80 N/cm². In case of dotted line graph, the sample was prepared in the same way, but the pull-off strength was measured at 60 °C. When the prepared sample was heated over the melting temperature, the wall pattern on the surface was recovered. As a result, the contact between cured PCO and glass disappeared, and the self-peeling occurred.

The smart composite surface with in-situ tunable adhesion was also fabricated using a similar method to that used for patterning micro-pillars on the SMP films. Their tunable adhesion behavior is under examination and will be presented at the conference.

4 Summary

We fabricated SMP films with micro-pillared surface and characterized their shape memory properties, demonstrating good shape memory characteristics. We will combine the shape memory behavior of the SMP with the surface patterning method and will fabricate a smart surface that can change its surface morphology and adhesion reversibly.

Fig. 1. The chemical structures of (a) Polycyclooctene(PCO) and (b) Dicumyl peroxide(DCP)

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of illustrating the characterization procedure of micro-pillared surface.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of illustrating bending test of the micro-pillars.

Fig. 4. Thermo-mechanical shape memory behavior of the SMPs in 3D plot

Fig. 5. Thermograms of cured PCO

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram describing the confinement effect of the crosslink to crystallization

Fig. 7. Thermo-mechanical shape memory behavior of SMPs in 2D plot

Fig. 8. Optical images of (a) original shape (b) deformed shape at 7th cycle(c) recovered shape after 7th cycle

Fig. 9. AFM image of patterned surface on SMP

Fig. 10 SEM image of the SMP films with micro-pillars

Fig. 11 Optical images of (a) original shape (b) deformed shape (c) recovered shape

Fig. 12. In-situ SEM image of pillar deformation in nano-indenter

Fig. 13. Stress-strain curve of a shape memory pillar

Fig. 14. Variation of contact angles according to micro-pillar geometry

Fig. 15. Variation of the contact angles according to the programming procedure of the SMP

Fig. 16. Effect of preload on the pull-off strength.

Fig. 17. The pull-off strength vs displacement curve of the cured PCOs.

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